

What is a personal umbrella data management plan (puDMP)?

A puDMP applies to all research that is not covered by a project-specific DMP, and negates the need to produce a new DMP for each new research project. The puDMP template can be found [here](#), or alternatively the standard Leiden DMP template can also be used.

More information on the puDMP template can be found in section 2.2 of the Institute Policy.

Important: A personal umbrella data management plan is not a project-specific DMP, nor is it accepted by funders. For these, please use the standard Leiden DMP template found [here](#).

About this document

This document provides a walk-through of how to create your puDMP. The text in **green** explains what each (sub-)section means, and how it can be filled out.

Please do not use this document as a template: This is written as a guide, and you should use the separate template to fill out your puDMP.

About the puDMP template

The puDMP template consists of three main sections: ‘Overview’, ‘Methodology Type:’, ‘Additional Information’.

‘Overview’ and ‘Additional Information’ are expanded by default, as these are a mixture of documentation- and perseverance-related questions that remain constant across all methodologies.

‘Methodology Type:’ Delete any methodologies that you do not use. Expand any methods that you do use and fill out/amend the pre-filled sections where necessary. After you are done, collapse the methodology type. When you submit a puDMP as part of a publication package, you can expand the relevant PDF sections and save a PDF version of the template.

puDMP Guide

0. Administrative details		
0.1	Contact details	Add your full name and email address here
0.2	ORCID	Add your ORCID. This can be found on your university profile page, or via https://orcid.org/ (please register via this link if you do not already have an ORCID).
0.3	Name of data management support staff consulted	Katie Hudson, Data Steward
0.4	Date of consultation with support staff	This is filled in by the data steward upon review

1. Data collection	
Describing the data you will be creating/collecting	
1.1	<p>Personal Data</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> I do not collect personal data.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> I collect personal data and I will contact the privacy officer before the start of data collection.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> I collect personal data and I have filled out a Data Processing Register for Research.</p> <p>Personal data refers to any data that pertains to an individual. This includes, but is not limited to, names, contact information, (email/IP) addresses, demographic information, audiovisual materials, et cetera. This includes data that may not be personally identifiable on its own, but in combination with other available data becomes identifiable.</p> <p>If you are collecting any information from participants, even if you intend to make this information anonymous, you should select an 'I collect personal data' option. If you are using personal data that is already publicly available, you can select 'I do not collect personal data'.</p>
1.2	<p>Will you use existing or third party data ?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Own / group previous research</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Academic collaborators</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Commercial collaborators</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Publicly available database / archive</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Specialist commercial data provider</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify)</p> <p><i>If you will use existing or third party data describe briefly origin and type of existing data.</i></p> <p>Existing or third party data refers to projects using secondary data. Here you can make a selection based on where your data is sourced from.</p> <p>Where data has been acquired from a database/archive that is not public (i.e. exists behind a paywall or access restrictions) please select 'other' and explain the source and access conditions it sets. Select 'other' for non-digital archives and specify the location.</p> <p>.....</p>
1.3	<p>Is there an agreement for the use of existing data?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes, I have a data transfer agreement (DTA)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes, this is written down in a consortium agreement</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes, this is written down in a research agreement</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes, other (please specify)</p> <p><i>Indicate if there any restrictions or requirements for use of this data, such as licensing conditions, informed consents, credits for data providers, permission to merge datasets?</i></p> <p>When you are collecting the data yourself, or the data are publicly available, you can select 'no'.</p> <p>If the data belongs to a third party and has restricted access, you may need to make an agreement to specify how the data can be transferred. If your are unsure about whether this is necessary, please contact the data steward.</p> <p>If a third party is involved in a specific project, the puDMP must be adjusted to account for this. This includes working with researchers at another Dutch University.</p> <p>...</p>
1.4	<p>How will you collect and/or create your data?</p> <p><i>Describe the research methodology.</i></p>

	Think about what your standard practices are for your chosen methodology. A basic description has already been pre-filled in the puDMP template, which you can adjust based on your own practice and the hardware/software you most frequently use.
1.5	<p>What type(s) of data will you collect and create, and in what file format(s)? <i>Consider also the data created by the processing of the raw data. See 'Tips and tricks' for types of data and sustainable formats.</i></p> <p>This refers to whether data will include audio, visual, numerical or other digital/physical formats. As above, think about your standard practice.</p>
1.6	<p>What tools, instruments, equipment, hardware or software will you use to capture, produce, collect, create and process the data? <i>Please give the names of the tools and state if they are already available. If not, state how you intend to acquire them. If applicable, describe whether you use a paper or electronic labjournal.</i></p> <p>This refers to any hardware or tools you use in collecting and/or processing and/or analysing the data.</p>

2. Data storage and security	
Ensuring that all research data are stored securely and backed up or copied regularly during your research	
2.1	<p>Are there any commercialisation, ethical or confidentiality restrictions about handling your data during your research?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><i>Please describe restrictions (e.g. contractual obligations, copyright, intellectual property, patentability, protection of personal data (privacy law), ethical restrictions, informed consent, institutional policies)</i></p> <p>The most common consideration is GDPR, which applies when personal data is collected; in this case, select 'yes' and state GDPR in this information box.</p> <p>If the data used are not publicly available, state the existing agreement for its use or access conditions here.</p>
2.2	<p>In accordance to data security measures, you will:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Lock raw data and version documents to avoid deletion/overwriting/version loss. This locked raw data will be securely in an environment that is routinely backed-up. <input type="checkbox"/> As above, the personal data of participants will be securely stored. Access restrictions will be applied to this data. <input type="checkbox"/> Should a data leak or unauthorised access occur, you will follow Leiden's Data Breach Protocol https://www.staff.universiteit leiden.nl/ict/privacy-and-data-protection/personal-data/privacy-and-data-breaches/service-units/administration-and-central-services?cf=service-units&cd=administration-and-central-services</p> <p>The first box should always be selected. If the research involves personal data, please select the second and third option in line with GDPR compliance.</p>
2.3	<p>Where will you store your data during your research? <i>Multiple answers possible.</i></p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> On university departmental network storage / workgroups (J:) <input type="checkbox"/> Physical storage (e.g. USB, external hard drive) <input type="checkbox"/> Research Drive <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional service (e.g. Dataverse), namely: <input type="checkbox"/> Other, namely: ...</p> <p>J: drive is the recommended platform. There is some flexibility as to where non-personal data is stored, so this is up to your personal preference. However, personal data <u>MUST</u> be stored securely with access restrictions, so a workable storage solution should be discussed with your data steward. Please see section 4.3 of the Institute Policy for acceptable storage solutions.</p>

	<p>Some research will involve the physical storage of data during its collection, for example interviews prior to transcription, images taken in the field, etc. For such projects, you can select the ‘physical storage’ option.</p> <p>Should the sensitivity of the data require offline storage, please elaborate this here and contact the data steward.</p>
2.4	<p>How will your data be backed up? <i>Please specify briefly for each storage device frequency, location of backups and who is responsible.</i></p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> I store my data on the university network storage which is backed-up by the ISSC. <input type="checkbox"/> I have my own provision which I describe below.</p> <p>The J: drive is securely backed-up by the ISSC. If your locked raw data is stored here, please select the first option. If data will not be stored on the J: drive, please state what backup mechanism your storage solution provides.</p>
2.5	<p>Are there any non-digital data or outputs that the project will generate? Where will these outputs be stored? <i>Do you have a protocol for the storage and deletion of non-digital data? Please specify briefly and describe who is responsible for storage of these outputs.</i></p> <p>Here you should think about any notes taken throughout fieldwork/data collection, any printed or physical materials used, any work that you will be doing by hand. Please state whether these materials will be digitised, and if not where they will be stored (particularly if these contain personal information, e.g. signed consent forms from participants).</p>

3. Data access and sharing Managing access and security, sharing your data	
3.1	<p>Are any restrictions placed on sharing your data? <i>Please account for not sharing (parts of) your data.</i></p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> I have no restrictions <input type="checkbox"/> I have restrictions on sharing (parts of) my data but I will share at least the metadata. Restrictions are due to:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Protection of personal data <input type="checkbox"/> Intellectual property <input type="checkbox"/> Copyright <input type="checkbox"/> Commercial reasons <input type="checkbox"/> Security-related issues <input type="checkbox"/> Ethical issues <input type="checkbox"/> Other (explain):</p> <p>As above, when personal data is collected you should select the ‘protection of personal data’ option. In the description box, you should clarify what your standard data sharing practices are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - whether anonymized data can be shared, such as survey results or interview transcripts with identifiable information removed, and the identification key destroyed. - if your data is generally too sensitive or it is too difficult to anonymize, consider if it can be pseudonymized and shared but under restricted access. If this is not possible, metadata can be provided as a minimum. <p>These two abovementioned points will be dependent on the conditions you set in your informed consent. If you work with a standard consent template across projects, sharing conditions will remain mostly constant.</p> <p>When the data is not personal data, there are generally no restrictions in how it can be shared. Any concerns about this can be directed to the data steward. For secondary data, including in the publication a persistent identifier or link for the data source is sufficient.</p>
3.2	<p>Do your participant consent forms include information about sharing, retention and deletion of data?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Not applicable. For projects that don’t collect personal data</p>

	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes. For projects that do collect personal data
3.3	<p>What conditions do you set when you share your data? Describe the criteria that you apply to give access to your data, such as use limited to specific purposes, security measures, deletion after use, credits etc. Have these conditions been defined in a consortium or data sharing agreement (or equivalent)?</p> <p>As above: personal data will not be shared/shared with restricted access depending on your general practices.</p> <p>Accompanying materials (e.g. codebooks, interview guides) can be shared openly upon publication as a standard practice.</p>

4. Data preservation and publication Preserving your data and making it FAIR	
4.1	<p>How long should your data be preserved? According to the University regulations on data management you must make your data findable, accessible and reusable for at least 10 years after the closure of a project . State any other obligations set by law, funder, etc. if any.</p> <p>As per Leiden University's data retention policy, a minimum of 10 years.</p>
4.2	<p>Are there any requirements regarding the destruction of data (digital and non-digital)? If personal data is collected, you must adhere to the informed consent you use (i.e. if you state in the informed consent that data will be deleted within a certain timeframe, state that here).</p> <p>For all other data, there are generally no restrictions as to whether it needs to be destroyed. Ideally, all physical data would be digitised and the hardcopies destroyed, but this is not a requirement if infeasible to do so.</p>
4.3	<p>Which of the following will you use for long-term findability and availability of your data?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> I will deposit data in a trusted data repository (e.g. DANS Easy, 4TU.ResearchData) as indicated below:</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> According to the data protocol of my institute, I will archive data in the data repository indicated below (e.g. Dataverse):</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> I will deposit data in a discipline-specific data repository as indicated below:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> I will use an archive specifically for my collaboration, namely:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> I will not use a data repository and will explain below how I will make my data findable and accessible for the long term.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> I will not make my data findable and accessible and I will explain why.</p> <p>A DataverseNL instance for the Institute has been created, which is what we will use as standard practice. If you would like to archive the data in an additional location, that is also fine and can be stated here.</p>
4.4	<p>What will you do to prepare your data for archiving? Will there be extra costs for this preparation? Please consult the Institute's Research Data Management and Open Science policy for more information about archiving procedure.</p> <p>For preparing the data for preservation (including the preparation of the publication package) the data steward will aid in the preparations. There are no additional costs here.</p> <p>For researchers consistently working on larger/long-term projects using student assistants, you can mention their role in the preparation of the data here.</p>
4.5	<p>Describe your strategy for publishing software that will be generated Indicate whether potential users need specific tools or software (e.g. specific scripts, codes or algorithms developed during the project) to access, interpret and (re-)use the data.</p> <p>If your research generates software, please specify how this is published. This includes the underlying code/script/algorithm, the license under which the software is released, et cetera.</p>
4.6	<p>What license will you apply to your data?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> I will use the default license of the repository, namely:</p>

	<input type="checkbox"/> I will use a creative common license, namely: CC-BY <input type="checkbox"/> I will use an open source licence, namely: <input type="checkbox"/> Other
	<p>The recommended standard license would be a type CC-BY, as this allows your data to be reused and adapted by others. When uploading the publication package, a more project-specific type of CC-BY can be specified.</p> <p>There are many forms of licences that allow varying levels of reuse if a CC-BY is not appropriate for your work. To explore which option you prefer, you can contact the licensing experts as CDS: auteursrecht@library.leidenuniv.nl</p>

5. Data documentation	
Documenting your data to help future users to understand and reuse it	
5.1	<p>What standard will you use to describe your data? <i>Please refer to any metadata standards in your field if they exist.</i></p> <p> <input type="checkbox"/> I have a discipline-specific metadata standard, namely: ... <input type="checkbox"/> Archival metadata standard (e.g. Dublin Core), namely: ... <input type="checkbox"/> Other metadata standard, namely: ... <input type="checkbox"/> I have my own documentation which I will describe below. </p> <p>Metadata is the data describing your data: It should provide all the information necessary to understand and interpret the data underlying your publication.</p> <p>This is most commonly stored as a README file (i.e. a separate file that accompanies your publication, containing the relevant information). The university recommends Dublin Core as the format for this file.</p> <p>For research that results in a publication package, the institute has developed a template of the necessary metadata for DataverseNL, which you can fill out via a formdesk form. If this is not appropriate for the data you generally collect, you can list your chosen metadata standard here.</p>
5.2	<p>What supporting information / documentation will be needed to understand and reuse the data <i>Please describe briefly how peers should be able to understand the data. Examples are lab journals, a codebook, survey questions, software documentation, readme.txt etc. Some institutes have mandatory publication packages.</i></p> <p>If you wish to elaborate beyond the text provided in the template, you can list the accompanying materials that you usually generate.</p>

6. Costs	
Estimate costs for data management during and after the project	
6.1	<p>Do you foresee additional research data management costs involved during and after this project? <i>E.g. additional storage, data curation or archiving costs.</i></p> <p> <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, namely: <input type="checkbox"/> No </p> <p>The services of the data steward come at no additional cost. The majority of projects therefore fall under the 'no' category.</p> <p>If you work on projects that required storage exceeding 1TB, additional costs will be involved and the first option should be selected.</p>

7. Additional information	
7.1	<p>Here you can put any additional information that you were not able to list in the boxes above.</p>

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